

PROVIDING THE ACTIVE INTEGRATION OF THE STATE LANGUAGE INTO MODERN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND COMMUNICATIONS

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Abstract: Today, when a new approach is being taken to the study of our rich national heritage, the topic under study is relevant, because the demand for experts who perfectly master a foreign language is increasing, because they serve as an important factor in revealing the secrets of our spiritual heritage. As a result of the complete mastery of the subject, the ability to read foreign language texts correctly, to understand the meaning of words and phrases to which period they belong, and to deepen theoretical knowledge of language grammar is considered.

Keywords: computer technologies, discs, electronic textbooks, multimedia tools, thematic websites, network encyclopedias, galleries, museums, virtual tours of educational institutions

In recent years, the issue of using new information technologies is becoming more and more important. These are not only modern technical tools, but also new forms of teaching, perhaps a new approach to the educational process. The use of multimedia tools helps students to implement a new approach to learning, provides individualization and differentiation, taking into account the student's characteristics, educational level, and abilities.

In our time, computer technology is a very important and independent tool. Many children and even adults use it only to play computer games. But, fortunately, many people have found a way to use it properly. The presence of such an assistant in our hands makes our work easier and saves our time, because we can print theses, reports and all the necessary things without leaving home.

In addition, the computer helps in learning a foreign language.

Today, when a new approach is being taken to the study of our rich national heritage, the topic under study is relevant, because the demand for specialists who perfectly master a foreign language is increasing, because they serve as an important factor in revealing the secrets of our spiritual heritage. As a result of the complete mastery of the subject, the ability to read foreign language texts correctly, to understand the meaning of words and phrases to which period they belong, and to deepen theoretical knowledge of language grammar is considered.

Language is an important means of mutual understanding and influence among people of different nationalities.

The main and most important function of language is communication: to convey certain information, knowledge, messages, facts and feelings between people. The main environment in which this communication takes place is the family, then neighbors and relatives, then school, work, public and private offices, etc. Most people use international languages not as their mother tongue (that is, not in the family), but only for educational purposes, for social and professional communication. For example, 2 billion people learn English today, 1.7 billion of whom use it as a second or foreign language. This determines both the character of the language and the content of communication in it.

Taking into account the above-mentioned feature of the Uzbek language, it is possible to define two large and partially overlapping spheres of communication. The first zone of communication, starting from the family environment, is the sphere of daily communication in oral language. It is formed according to the specific characteristics of a certain family, neighborhood, village and district. The only way to access this communication is to become part of a particular family or a particular place and environment. If you come from another region, city or country, then you are a stranger, you will be treated as a guest.

Such communication within the family is the basis of Uzbek culture, and it remains very closed to others. Thick walls surrounding houses in neighborhoods can

be a clear example of this. A large number of weddings serve for wide communication. The main purpose of holding them is to generalize the members of various groups, families and associations.

This system does not need much help from the state or the outside world. While it does not strive for development or expansion, it creates a spacious and comfortable environment for its members to thrive in return for strengthening internal ties. Here, kinship and neighborly relations prevail over friendly and professional relations.

The second circle of communication is formed by the state. It is implemented through orders, statements, messages, news, as well as from the meetings of the Oliy Majlis to the conversation with the Domkom, using the documents and communications related to a large number of organizations that arise in the process of management and administration through texts that are strictly controlled from top to bottom. This circle extends in all directions below. Connecting with the first circle, it forms various contexts and forms of communication (the most common — professional and educational activities).

The unique feature of the Uzbek language in this context is the integration of centralization and normativeness, realized with the understanding of going beyond the borders of a narrow national discourse. The practice of centralization cannot be caused only by the presence of other ethnic groups and linguistic associations in the country. It should be noted here that there are wide layers of meaning, in which ideas and contents first appeared in other languages and then were translated into Uzbek. When we talk about the place and status of the Uzbek language, we cannot ignore its interaction with other languages. In some regions of Uzbekistan, the Uzbek language is used alongside the Karakalpak and Tajik languages or gives way to them.

The majority of Karakalpak speakers live in a relatively remote and well-defined area. Tajik speakers live in the central and southern parts of Uzbekistan. In addition to the well-known Samarkand and Bukhara, they also live in Denov, Ferghana Valley and other districts. Almost all of them use two languages

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